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ABSTRACT

Abstract text

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

C/N	Carbon to Nitrogen atomic ratio
DM	Dry matter
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse gas

H/C_{org} Hydrogen to organic carbon atomic ratio
NH₄ Ammonium
NMR Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
NO₃ Nitrate
NPK Synthetic fertilizer
TGA Thermogravimetric analysis
WP Work Package

1. Introduction

Anaerobic digestion is a common process in the industry to treat organic waste. It promotes several benefits, including biogas production, waste stabilization, nutrient recovery, and pathogen reduction. This technique associated with composting can create valuable products for regenerative agriculture as an organic fertilizer. Also, adding biochar to the production of these organic fertilizers can be helpful as it can potentially increase nutrient retention and microbial activity and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Nonetheless, the outcomes of combinations among these techniques for producing nutrient-rich and stable fertilizers are still highly unknown. This study aims to understand the role of anaerobic digestion and biochar application on composted substrates from food waste and animal manure in producing nutrient-rich and stable fertilizers with the potential to mitigate GHG.

1.1 Choice of waste streams and processing methods

Nearly 50% of food waste generated in the capital of Norway is currently recycled through anaerobic digestion. Furthermore, the nation aims to use the same processing of 30% of all animal manure. Energy production in the form of biogas is the main aim of anaerobic digestion, while the digestate byproduct is nutrient-rich with potential for use in place of synthetic fertilizers. In the experiments, we obtained substrate and dewatered digestate (up to 35% dry matter content) from Den Magiske Fabrikken in Telemark, Norway, as it provided a representative sample of waste types utilized by biogas plants. The substrate, having a dry matter content of 14%, consisted of 49% household food waste, 5 % industrial waste (blood, fat, etc.), and 46 % manure (composting of 54 % cow manure, 32 % of pig manure and the rest a mixture of cow and pig manure).

Aerobic composting is labor intensive and does not produce an energy co-product, but the compost product is thought to be superior for soil amendment. Here, we evaluated the fertilizer replacement value of the waste sources mentioned above after they had gone through either anaerobic digestion, composting, or both.

1.2 Linking waste treatment to quality of the soil amendment

This study focuses on the quality of fertilizer replacement products in terms of their ability to provide nutrients for food production. GHG emissions during processing and when applied as fertilizer are similarly crucial. We took a holistic approach by measuring GHG emissions during composting and upon application to soil to evaluate net emissions. In this way, possible tradeoffs between the fertilizer replacement value and climate impact could be assessed.

2. Main text

2.1. Methods

Method descriptions of the experimental work are presented below.

2.1.1 Composting trial

Compost was produced from substrate or digestate, with and without biochar addition. The four treatments were replicated three times each. Composts made from substrate consisted of a mix of substrate (30 L), wood shavings (65 L), and wood chips (20 L). Compost made from digestate consisted of a mix of digestate (70 L) and wood chips (20 L). Wood shavings were used to increase the C/N ratio, and wood chips were used for structural purposes. This resulted in a starting mixture having a C/N ratio of 24 for the substrate mix and a C/N ratio of 27.8 for the digestate mix. We prioritized having the same total dry weight of material in the digestate and the substrate treatment over obtaining the same C/N ratio.

Biochar was obtained from Novo Carbo, which used mixed wood as feedstock and Pyreg technology for the pyrolysis. The resulting biochar had an H/Corg atomic ratio of 0.44. Further properties of the biochar can be found in Weldon et al. (2022). The biochar was added based on dry weight (5 % DW of the total mix), corresponding to 3 L in volume. This volume was compensated in the treatment without biochar by adding 3 L of wood shavings.

Figure 1: Schematics of the Experiment Treatments. Designed with Biorender.

The composting experiment was conducted in rotating composting units (tumblers), each consisting of two 135 L chambers with insulated walls (Joraform 270, Sweden). The chamber side walls each had two sections of 10 cm² aeration holes. Composts were turned daily during the thermophilic stage (3 weeks above 50 °C with peaks above 65 °C) and then turned every second week during the maturation phase (about 6 months). GHG production was assessed

during the composting process. Composts were sampled throughout the composting process and analyzed. The matured compost product was sieved at 4mm and analyzed for chemical and physical properties. Carbon quality was assessed using thermogravimetric methods, as described further below.

2.1.2 Pot experiment

Although we had 12 composting chambers in total, only 4 chambers corresponding to one of each treatment were used to test in the pot experiment: Compost of substrate (chamber 8), compost of substrate with biochar (chamber 3), compost of digestate (chamber 5), and compost of digestate with biochar (chamber 7). There were, in addition, three more treatments: one unfertilized control, one treatment with mineral NPK fertilization (22-3-10), and one with non-composted fresh digestate.

Each pot (16.5 cm diameter, 13.5 cm depth) consisted of 2.6 kg of fresh soil at a DM of 85%. The loamy soil, with 1.5% organic matter content, was collected in an agricultural field in Ås, Norway. The soil was sieved at 1 cm and thoroughly homogenized.

Compost was added based on total nitrogen content (after CHN analysis) to meet an equivalent of 13 kg N/da (280 mg N/pot, based on the pot's surface). We assumed this to be the expected fertilizer requirement and equated it to a 100% fertilization rate. For each compost treatment and the fresh digestate treatment, three sub-treatments corresponded to a 50% fertilization rate, a 100% fertilization rate, and a 200% fertilization rate. The NPK treatments had three sub-treatments corresponding to 25%, 50%, and 100% fertilization rates. Each treatment had 5 replicates, bringing the total number of pots to 95. The experiment was started on January 29th (day 0) and lasted until April 11th (day 68). Seeds (Italian ryegrass, mandora) were sown on day 2 at 0.08 g/pot and covered with horticultural fleece until germination (day 5). All pots were equipped with a plastic liner to avoid nutrient leaching and were watered to 70% of the maximum water holding capacity (mWHC) based on weight.

Soil samples were taken four times: all 95 pots were sampled on days 0 and 68, while only two of the five replicates were sampled on days 27 and 48. Soils were analyzed for soil nutrient content and microbial community composition. Plant biomass was harvested from three of the five replicates, which corresponded with the soil sampling dates.

2.1.3 GHG analysis

Gas sampling during the composting trial involved removing the temperature sensors and rotating all tumblers before opening for aeration of the headspace with a fan for 30 s. Chambers were then made airtight, and a syringe was used through a sampling port to collect 20 mL of gas from the headspace at intervals of 10 min over 30 min.

Gas sampling during the plant growth experiment was performed 15 times: once a day during the first week, including "day 1", every other day during the second week, and up to every 10 days as sampling frequency was reduced toward the end of the experiment. Nine custom-built chambers were used to encompass individual pots during the sampling period. The headspace

of the chambers was mixed using a fan before sampling 20 mL of headspace using a syringe, and each sampling consisted of four-time points at 1, 15, 30, and 45 minutes.

Samples were stored in previously evacuated glass vials at overpressure for analysis. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and methane (CH₄) concentrations were determined by gas chromatography (GC Agilent 7890A, Agilent Technologies, Germany), using a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) for CO₂ and N₂O concentrations above 4 ppm, a flame ionization detector (FID) for CH₄, and an electron capture detector (ECD) for N₂O concentrations below 4 ppm. Two standard gas mixes with certified CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O concentrations were analyzed every 8 samples to enable the conversion of peak areas into ppm. The low standard contained 398.6 ppm CO₂, 1.96 ppm CH₄, and 0.549 ppm N₂O, and the high standard 2004.8 ppm CO₂, 99.5 ppm CH₄, and 4.9 ppm N₂O.

2.1.4 Soil nutrient analysis

Soil and compost ammonium (NH₄-N) and nitrate (NO₃-N) were extracted with 2M KCl solution, and their concentrations were measured by spectrophotometric methods using a SEAL analyzer, with a limit of detection of 0.01 mg N l⁻¹. Ca, Mg, and Na were extracted by a 1 N ammonium acetate solution at pH 7. Available P was extracted with a 0.1M ammonium lactate solution. Total P was extracted with a Mehlich-3 solution. Nutrients were quantified using Inductively Coupled Plasma Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). Compost pH was measured in a 0.01 CaCl₂ solution using a pH meter. C and N contents of soil and compost were measured by dry combustion using a CN analyzer.

2.1.5 Plant sampling

Plant biomass was harvested by cutting all ryegrass 5 cm above the soil surface. The biomass was dried at 40°C before dry mass determination.

2.1.6 Plant nutrient analysis

Ten milligrams of the sample were weighed into a tin capsule. The capsule with the sample was folded and placed in a CHNS-O (ECS 4010—Elemental Combustion System) elemental analyzer autosampler. The sample was burned through helium (He) gas combustion. The He flow rate was 110 ml/min, the left furnace temperature was 1020 °C, and the right furnace temperature was 800 °C. The results were processed using the “Elemental analysis software” program.

2.1.7 Assessing microbial Metabarcoding of 16S and ITS2

Soil samples were collected in duplicate from two pots for each of the 100% fertilization rate treatments (Dig100, C-Dig100, C-DigBC100, Sub100, SubBC100), as well as from control and NPK50 treatments at three-time points: day 1, day 21, and day 43. This resulted in a total of 84 samples. DNA was extracted from 250 mg of soil using the Qiagen PowerSoil Kit, following the manufacturer's instructions. The DNA concentration was measured using a Nanodrop 2000, and all samples were diluted to a concentration of 2 ng/μL. The bacterial 16S rRNA (V4-

V5 region) and fungal ITS2 regions were targeted for amplification using primers 515F/806R and ITS2F/ITS4, respectively. PCR amplification was performed in 20 μL reactions containing 2 ng of DNA, 0.2 μL of Platinum HotStart DNA polymerase, 10 μL of 10X Platinum HotStart DNA polymerase buffer, 1 μL each of 10 μM forward and reverse primers, and 7.8 μL of Milli-Q H₂O. The PCR conditions included an initial enzyme activation step at 94°C for 3 minutes, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 50°C (for 16S) or 52°C (for ITS2) for 30 seconds, and extension at 72°C for 30 seconds. Successful amplification was confirmed via gel electrophoresis on a 1.5% agarose gel stained with SYBR Safe. The bacterial and fungal amplicon libraries were pooled and sequenced using the Illumina MiSeq platform with 300-bp paired-end reads (MiSeq 300-bp chemistry).

After quality filtering, including the removal of sequences containing ambiguous bases (Ns), the sequencing run yielded a total of 14,302,071 bacterial reads and 10,722,157 fungal reads. Post-denoising, merging, and removal of chimeric sequences, 6,514,483 bacterial and 8,621,332 fungal sequences remained. Taxonomic classification was performed using the SILVA (for bacterial sequences) and UNITE (for fungal sequences) databases, the dataset was further pruned by removing any species with ≥ 100 reads. To correct for different sequencing depths, all samples were rarefied to 20 000 reads per sample.

2.1.8 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

TGA analyses were performed using a Simultaneous thermal analysis (STA 449 F1 Jupiter, Sant Joan Despí, Spain). Samples were placed in a crucible with a weight equivalent to 1 mg of C. Samples were heated at 105 °C for 10 min to remove all sample moisture. The samples were then combusted with increasing temperatures at 10 °C per minute until 900 °C. The samples were maintained at 900 °C for 10 minutes to guarantee the complete combustion of all degradable compounds at this temperature range. The mass of the samples was monitored during the combustion process, and the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) represented the heat flow associated with thermal events such as endothermic and exothermic reactions. Based on the mass loss curves, we calculated the T50 index, which corresponds to the temperature at which 50% of the mass of the sample is lost.

2.1.9 ¹³C CPMAS NMR

The carbon molecular composition of each organic fertilizer was evaluated through ¹³C cross-polarization magic angle spinning (CPMAS) nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy (Bruker DSX 200, Bruker BioSpin GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany). Samples were inserted in 7-mm zirconium dioxide rotors and spun in a magic angle spinning probe at 6.8 KHz and 0.01024s acquisition time. The spectra were divided into the following functional groups: 0-45 ppm (alkyl C), 45–110 ppm (O/N alkyl C), 110–160 ppm (aromatic C), and 160–220 ppm (carboxyl C).

2.1.10 Statistical analyses

Data was analyzed using one-way ANOVA. When ANOVA indicated significant differences, averages were compared with a post hoc test of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) at a significance level 0.05. Simple linear regressions between yield and NH₄ and NO₃ contents were analyzed, and the significance level was assessed by examining the p-value.

3. Findings

3.1 Nutrient qualities of the four compost products

Digestate with or without biochar presented significantly higher amounts of available P, total P, Ca, Mg, and higher pH than substrate. On the other hand, substrate presented significantly higher amounts of NO₃, NO₂, and Na than digestate. The addition of biochar had a minor influence on these nutrient amounts.

Table 1: Nutrient amounts composted digestate (C-dig) and substrate (C-Sub) from manure and food waste and their mixes with biochar (C-Dig-BC and C-Sub-BC). Every treatment is an average of 3 replicates (composting drums). Different uppercase letters indicate significant differences according to the LSD test at $p < 0.05$.

Nutrients	C-Dig	C-Sub	C-Dig-BC	C-Sub-BC
NH ₄ (mg kg ⁻¹)	27.66 B	30.66 B	15.00 B	36.00 B
Available P (mg g ⁻¹)	9.9A	2.16 B	8.6 A	2.1 B
K (mg g ⁻¹)	3.46 B	6.30 B	3.76 B	4.82 B
Ca (mg g ⁻¹)	38.33 A	12.66 B	35.33 A	13.33 B
Mg (mg g ⁻¹)	6.36 A	1.56 B	6.13 A	1.46 A
Na (mg g ⁻¹)	1.33 B	2.76 A	1.40 B	2.93 A
NO ₃ + NO ₂ (mg kg ⁻¹)	60.00 B	453.33 A	75.00 B	550.00 A
pH (CaCl ₂)	8.56 A	7.93 B	8.66 A	7.63 B
Total N (mg g ⁻¹)	2.53 B	2.27 B	2.57 B	2.07 B
Total P (mg g ⁻¹)	17.33 A	4.90 C	12.33 B	4.43 C
Total C (mg g ⁻¹)	380.00 B	420.00 AB	386.66 B	446.66 A

3.2 Nutrient recovery/availability

3.2.1 Plant yield data

Fresh digestate outperformed NPK during the 1st harvest, assuming all N is readily available to plants in the synthetic fertilizer and only half in digestate. Composted products produced lower yields at all application rates than the NPK treatments (Figure Xa). Biochar addition during composting slightly increased yield during the 1st harvest, where composts were applied at higher rates (100 and 200% of the assumed fertilization requirement), but the differences were insignificant.

Fresh digestate no longer outperformed NPK during consecutive harvests but performed better than the composts (Figure Xb, Xc). Biochar addition during composting did not significantly improve nutrient availability in the composted product, as greater yield was not obtained for these treatments.

Figure 2 : Dry weight of ryegrass harvested during the 1st, 2nd and 3rd harvests (a, b, c) during a pot experiment where no fertilizer was applied (control), synthetic fertilizer (NPK) was applied at 25, 50, and 100% of the estimated fertilizer requirement, and and digestate (Dig), composted digestate (C-Dig), composted digestate with biochar (C-Dig-BC), composted substrate (C-Sub), composted substrate with biochar addition (C-Sub-BC) were applied at twice these fertilizer requirement rates (50, 100, and 200). n=5. Different uppercase letters indicate significant differences according to the LSD test at $p < 0.05$.

3.1.2 Soil N availability

Soil nutrient status indicated the highest NH_4 and NO_3 concentrations upon NPK application (Figure X). The application of non-composted digestate led to similar NH_4 levels as the NPK treatments, while none of the composts applied reached higher values than the control (Figure Xa). Digestate did not contribute to increased NO_3 levels (Figure Xe). Biochar addition during composting did not contribute to increased soil mineral N when applied to soil.

Figure 3: Ammonium (left) and nitrate (right) content of soil sampled at the time of soil amendment (a, e), after 27 days (b, f), 48 days (c, g), and 68 days (d, h) of growth. N=5 for a, e, d, and h, while n=3 for b, c, f, and g. Different uppercase letters indicate significant differences according to the LSD test at $p < 0.05$.

By the end of the two-month experiment, both NH₄ and NO₃ were depleted in all treatments. The biomass produced correlates best with soil NH₄ levels at the start of the experiment.

Yield biomass can be explained primarily by the availability of inorganic nitrogen forms NH_4 and NO_3 (Figure x). NPK treatments were the main ones responsible for yield increases and the digestate treatments. Such results suggest that although the organic fertilizers were applied at high biomass rates, most of the nitrogen in their composition is organic and, therefore, not immediately available for plant nutrition. We have initially hypothesized that, due to the higher total N of organic fertilizers, the mineralization could occur over time and provide nutrients for plants, promoting higher yields at the second and third harvests. Nonetheless, such mineralization did not happen during the time scale of this experiment, which suggests that the mineralization of our composted organic fertilizers is slower than previously assumed.

Nonetheless, the non-composted digestate treatment presented comparable amounts of NH_4 with the NPK treatments, resulting in higher biomass yields than other composted treatments. Therefore, in the short term, non-composted digestate may be a better nitrogen source for plant nutrition than other options. However, the composting process may result in higher benefits for soil quality, which remains to be confirmed through soil quality analyses.

Figure 4: Correlation between NH_4 and NO_3 contents and the Yield biomass in the first Harvest.

3.2 Plant C and N contents

Figure 5: Plant C and N contents. Different uppercase letters indicate significant differences according to the LSD test at $p < 0.05$.

Plant C content has not varied according to the treatment. On the other hand, plant N content followed similar trends as yields, NH_4 , and NO_3 . NPK 100 has promoted the highest N content in plant tissue compared to other treatments. NPK 100 and Dig100 promoted the second-highest N content in plants. The composted treatments resulted in lower plant N contents, which did not differ from the control treatment.

The plant N contents were significantly influenced by the experiment's initial contents of NH_4 and NO_3 .

Figure 6: Correlation between initial contents of NH_4 and NO_3 and the plant N content.

3.3 Greenhouse gas emissions

3.3.1 Emissions during composting

Due to instrument issues that were never resolved, we could not obtain GHG measurements beyond the first week-and-a-half of the active composting phase. We also encountered problems with the temperature sensors used. From the initial CO_2 emissions, we can see that digestate started composting earlier than the substrate, but the substrate surpassed digestate in activity at the end of this short period. Variability in the N_2O emissions between the replicates was high in the initial phase, and the data are insufficient to conclude any treatment effect.

3.3.2 Emissions after application of compost to the soil in a pot trial

N_2O emissions were higher 10 days after the beginning of the pot experiment. Overall, higher emissions for the fresh digestate (F-Dig 100) treatment was noticed, but no significant difference in cumulative values was observed, likely due to the high variability of the data. No effect of biochar in reducing N_2O emissions was noticed during the pot experiment evaluation.

Figure 7: Cumulative N₂O emissions during the first 30 days of pot experiment.

3.4 Microbial community composition

Figure 8 : PCoA ordinations based on Bray Curtis dissimilarity matrix of 16S (bacteria) and ITS2 (fungal) rarefied (20000 reads) OTU table.

3.4.1 Influence on soil after compost application

Bacterial community composition.

Except for fresh digestate and, to a certain extent, the composted substrate and substrate+ biochar, the amendments did not significantly affect the community composition of the bacteria on day 1. The controls, NPK50, CDIG, and CDIG+BC, consistently clustered together, indicating that the community composition did not respond extensively to the soil amendments immediately after addition. This trend changed after 21 days; at this point, the bacteria from the Dig, NPK50, and Control samples had a more similar community composition, while the remaining treatments clustered together. After the end of the experiment, all added amendments showed a similar convergence regarding bacterial community composition, while the control and the NPK50 treatments were separated along PCoA axis 1.

Fungal community composition

The fungal dataset showed similar trends. On day 1, the fungal community composition was markedly different in the fresh digestate treatments. Sub and Sub+BC treatments also showed weak signs of separation, indicating a shift in community composition. This trend continued

throughout the first 3 weeks of the experiment. Dig50 samples were the most dissimilar concerning both bacterial and fungal community composition. This is most likely because the digestate was not composted; thus, the nutrient composition differed from that of the composted amendments. Moreover, incorporating the uncomposted digestate was more challenging, which may have resulted in a more variable recovery of microbial members.

In the bacterial dataset, the separation of the bacterial communities in the Dig50 samples was mainly due to the enrichment of a group in the Gammaproteobacteria order Pseudomonadales, including members of the families Moraxellaceae and Pseudomonadaceae. Unfortunately, these ASVs did not have a taxonomic identification at the genus level, making any function assessment very difficult. The weak separation from some of the composted substrate samples was most likely due to the enrichment of the Pseudomonadales family Cellvibrionaceae. After 23 days, the bacterial community seemed to converge, but we failed to find any clear shift of specific bacterial groups that would explain this change.

However, on day 46, the community composition again showed a shift. This change was, at least partly, due to a large increase in the abundance of the bacterial genus *Acinetobacter*, a member of the Gammaproteobacterial order Pseudomonadales. *Acinetobacter* is commonly found in soils and compost, where the genus has an important role in the mineralization of aromatic compounds (Kong et al., 2020). Interestingly, this bacterial ASV was recovered on day 1 on the Dig50 treatments at relatively low abundances. We could not recover any bacteria from this genus at the second sampling time. However, this was among the most recovered bacterial ASV at day 46 in all the Substrate, substrate BC, digestate, and digestate BC amendment samples. In contrast, this group was not recovered in the control samples and at very low abundances in the NPK50 sample.

In the fungal dataset, the early stages of community shift were similar to the bacterial dataset. However, the changes were driven by a large increase in the abundance of an unidentified member of *Mycothermus thermophilus* (synonym *Scytalidium thermophilum*), a member of the Ascomycete order Sordariales. This species is a thermophilic fungus with optimum growing conditions at 45°; this fungus is consistently recovered in compost samples and is known to produce a diverse set of lignocellulose degrading enzymes, including trehalase, glucosidase, and arabinofuranosidases. The observed separation of the fungal community composition on day 1 of the Dig50 treatments was largely driven by the absence of core microbes found in the other treatments rather than unique fungal ASVs associated with this specific amendment. The aforementioned fungal groups continued to dominate after the second sampling points, where again compost-amended samples were dominated by *Mycothermus thermophilus*, while the Dig50 samples showed a relatively large increase in reads from the *Humicola grisea*, also a member of the Chaetomiaceae. Although there has been some work done on *Humicola grisea*, however, less is known about this fungus. *H. grisea* is likely thermophilic, and is capable of degrading complex lignocellulose materials (De-Paula et al. 1999). By day 46, the fungal community showed signs of convergence. However, we still

found several enriched groups, including *Conlarium* and *Schizothecium* in Dlg50, while *Cladosporium* was recovered at high read abundances in NPK50.

3.5 Carbon stability

3.5.1 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Figure 9: Thermogravimetric measurements of a) biochar made of Norwegian Spruce at 700 °C, b) uncomposted manure substrate, c) composted manure substrate, d) composted manure substrate with 10% of biochar, e) manure substrate processed through anaerobic digestion and composted (digestate), f) manure substrate processed through anaerobic digestion and composted (digestate) with 10% of biochar. The black line represents the mass of each treatment throughout the combustion process. Red dotted lines correspond to the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) curves, representing the heat flow associated with thermal events such as endothermic and exothermic reactions during the heating process. Each sample is composed by 4 technical replicates.

The mass loss curves indicate an initial decrease corresponding to the sample moisture as the samples are heated at 104 °C for 10 minutes. All the treatments present a steep mass decrease from 200 °C to 500 °C, illustrating their thermal decomposition pattern. The temperature rate and intensity at which these mass losses occurred varied depending on the treatment. The digestate treatment presented more gradual mass losses than other treatments, indicating a more homogeneous composition. The substrate, either composted or non-composted, and biochar presented a steeper mass loss divided into two distinct steps. Such steps of mass loss coincide with negative peaks of the DSC curve, indicating endothermic reactions. The negative DSC peak was more intense for the biochar sample, which presented a steep mass decrease at 345 °C.

Figure 10: T50 Index, the temperature at which 50% of the mass is degraded of non-composted substrate from non-composted manure substrate (Control), composted manure substrate, composted manure substrate with 10% of biochar, manure substrate processed through anaerobic digestion and co,mposted (digestate), manure substrate processed through anaerobic digestion and composted (digestate) with 10% of biochar, and pure biochar made of Norwegian Spruce at 700 o C. Different uppercase letters indicate significant difference by the LSD test at $p < 0.05$. $n = 4$.

Figure 2 illustrates the thermostability index T50, which indicates the temperature at which 50% of the sample mass is lost. The substrate treatment did not significantly differ from the non-composted substrate, indicating that the composting process performed minor roles in improving thermostability. On the other hand, digestate treatment presented significantly higher T50 indexes than the substrate, indicating that anaerobic digestion significantly improved the substrate thermostability. Biochar presented the highest T50 index, and as expected, its addition to substrate and digestate treatments increased their thermostability compared to their unamended versions despite the low amendment rate of 5%.

3.5.2 ¹³C CPMASC NMR

Figure 11: ¹³C CPMASC spectra a) biochar made of Norwegian Spruce at 700 °C, b) uncomposted manure substrate, c) composted manure substrate, d) composted manure substrate with 10% of biochar, e) manure substrate processed through anaerobic digestion and composted (digestate), f) manure substrate processed through anaerobic digestion and composted (digestate) with 10% of biochar. The chemical shift regions represent the following functional groups: 0–45 ppm (alkyl C), 45–110 ppm (O/N alkyl C), 110–160 ppm (aromatic C), and 160–220 ppm (carboxyl C). Numbers in each region correspond to their respective integral values, estimating their relative proportion.

The ¹³C CPMASC analyses give an overview of the treatment’s molecular composition. Biochar, as expected, is composed mainly of aromatic-C, while the non-composted substrate mostly comprises the O-Alkyl-C group, indicating its fresh organic matter nature. The substrate treatment (composted substrate) presents an overall higher Alkyl-C / O-Alkyl-C ratio (0.26 vs 0.17), suggesting a more advanced stage of decomposition resulting from the composting process. Such a higher ratio indicates a higher material stability as the alkyl-C group is known to persist longer in the environment (Nie et al., 2024). Nonetheless, such a difference in composition did not reflect a significantly higher thermostability as indicated by the T50 index. On the other hand, the digestate treatment presented an even higher Alkyl-C / O-Alkyl-C ratio (0.32) and a higher Carboxylic-C relative proportion than the substrate, indicating a higher degree of decomposition resulting from the anaerobic digestion. The higher proportion of the Carboxylic-C group is also an indicator of its persistence, as this group is recognized for promoting long-term persistence in soils (Yu et al., 2015), as well as promoting nutrient retention (Solly et al., 2020). As expected, since the biochar is composed primarily of aromatic-C, its addition to either digestate or substrate treatments resulted in a higher aromatic-C proportion in the biochar-amended treatments. As aromatic-C is considered one of the most stable forms of C in soils (Barré et al., 2016), its higher proportion in biochar is likely responsible for the higher thermostability observed in biochar-amended treatments.

3. Conclusions

NPK additions promoted significantly higher biomass yield in Italian Ryegrass, mainly induced by a significant increase of NO_3 and NH_4 compared to the unamended soil (control). Fresh digestate promoted comparable increases in yield with the NPK treatments. All other composted treatments, including digestate and substrate, with or without biochar, presented yield levels equivalent to a 25% NPK rate (NPK 25). Yield harvests decreased over time as the NO_3 and NH_4 contents depleted after 27 days for all treatments, including the NPK. Greenhouse gas emissions during composting time were not possible due to technical issues. During the pot experiment, we observed slightly higher levels of N_2O emissions for the fresh digestate, but the differences were insignificant. Bacteria and fungal communities presented distinguished compositions, especially for the fresh digestate treatment. These differences were highlighted at about 20 days of the pot trial and tended to diminish towards the end of the experiment. C stability analyses indicated that digestate had a higher thermostability than the substrate indicated by the T50 index. This higher thermostability was also concomitant with a higher carboxylic-C proportion and Alkyl-C/O-Alkyl-C ratio. Biochar addition was also demonstrated to promote a higher thermostability of both composted digestate and substrate, mainly due to increased Aromatic-C. In conclusion, organic fertilization, primarily through fresh digestate, presents an excellent potential to complement or even replace inorganic fertilization. Nonetheless, potential increases in N_2O emissions need to be observed in future experiments. Composted treatments presented lower yield levels due to lower NO_3 and NH_4 contents, but potential benefits for soil quality need to be confirmed to understand its benefits. Biochar addition has not presented yield or nutrient retention improvements in composted treatments. However, it presented benefits in improving the C stability of these organic fertilizers by increasing the relative proportion of Aromatic C.

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